

From Miniature to Metadata: Transferring AI-Assisted Iconography to Medieval Manuscripts

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Introduction

Assigning structured iconographic metadata like Iconclass to historical images is labor-intensive, requiring domain expertise, contextual insight, and time. This challenge is especially acute in richly illustrated medieval manuscripts, where iconographic complexity hampers large-scale interoperability and reuse. To address this, we introduce a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) pipeline that combines Large Language Models (LLMs) with vector search to semi-automate Iconclass classification.

Building on a method developed for early modern woodcuts, we test its adaptability to the distinct visual and material world of medieval manuscript miniatures. Our case study is the Wenzelsbibel, a monumental 14th-century German Bible whose digital edition encodes both text and image using TEI. We examine whether combining image embeddings with editorial descriptions can improve classification prompt generation and Iconclass precision.

Our goal is to assess whether this multimodal, RAG-based approach—anchored in expert validation and guided by machine learning—can support scalable, efficient application of structured iconography. Our evaluation demonstrates that the RAG-based pipeline delivers substantially stronger performance than both image-retrieval and keyword-search baselines, underscoring its value as a practical method for large-scale iconographic annotation.

Background and Related Work

The Wenzelsbibel¹

The WB (Vienna, Austrian National Library Cod. 2759–2764) is one of the most elaborate German-language Bibles

of the late 14th century. Commissioned by King Wenceslas IV of Germany and Bohemia, the manuscript consists of six volumes, 1,214 folios, and 654 main miniatures, in addition to extensive marginal decoration. Its importance lies not only in its visual opulence but also in its status as the first programmatic German, word-for-word translation of the Old Testament based on the Latin Vulgate. The manuscript is part of UNESCO's "Memory of the World" program and is the subject of the ongoing project "Wenzelsbibel – Digitale Edition und Analyse," led by the University of Salzburg in partnership with the Austrian National Library (The Wenceslas Bible, 2025).

This digital edition treats each page as an integrated visual-textual ensemble, encompassing not just main illustrations but also historiated initials, marginalia, and decorative elements. It uses TEI/XML for structural encoding and semantic annotation, aiming to document the complex intermedial relationships between images and text. One of the key challenges has been the consistent and scalable assignment of iconographic metadata to the manuscript's hundreds of miniatures.

Iconclass and the Need for Scalable Annotation

Iconclass is a hierarchical, multilingual classification system widely used for describing themes in Western art (Van de Waal, 1974–1985). While it offers a rich vocabulary, applying it to complex and layered medieval imagery is a difficult and time-consuming task that traditionally requires human expertise. For large manuscript corpora, this manual process becomes a major bottleneck in digital scholarship, limiting interoperability and searchability across collections.

Prior Work and Positioning in the Field

Recent years have seen a surge in computer vision and vision-language models applied to cultural heritage data. Projects like the Oxford Broadside Ballads (Bergel et al., 2017), Compositor (Wilkinson et al., 2021), and Ornamento (Wilkinson, 2022) have used object detection to identify illustrations and ornaments in early printed books, while others like SMKExplore (Meyer et al., 2024) and OmniArt (Strezoski and Worring, 2017) have built large benchmark datasets. These approaches, often relying on fine-tuned CNNs or multimodal models like CLIP (Radford et al., 2021), have successfully improved searchability and retrieval in large visual collections. In the context of Iconclass, some efforts have paired visual and textual features to predict iconographic codes, demonstrating the value of hybrid systems for complex classification tasks (Santini et al., 2024; Posthumus et al., 2022; Banar et al., 2021).

However, these models often depend on extensive training data and computational resources, limiting their accessibility for smaller or more specialized collections. Cultural heritage images also present challenges due to symbolic

content, inconsistent annotation, and historical variation. While many studies highlight the advantages of combining metadata with visual features, few move beyond feature extraction architectures.

Our earlier work proposed an alternative: a pipeline using LLMs to generate natural-language descriptions from page images, using those descriptions for semantic search and Iconclass retrieval via a RAG framework (Thomas 2024). Without training data or fine-tuning, this model achieved 87% and 92% precision at five and four Iconclass levels, respectively. Our aim is to improve and adapt that pipeline for medieval manuscript miniatures, testing the impact of metadata-augmented prompts and exploring the broader potential of text-first, low-resource methodologies.

Research Questions and Challenges

This project bridges digital art history, artificial intelligence, and editorial infrastructure. Rather than simply reusing an existing tool, we critically examine how a hybrid AI-human system can be adapted for low-data, high-complexity cultural heritage contexts. Our research focuses on the following questions:

1. **Transferability:** How effectively can an AI-based pipeline for iconographic classification be applied to medieval manuscript miniatures with distinct visual conventions and materials?
2. **Robustness:** What technical and interpretive challenges arise in this domain shift—particularly concerning visual embeddings, iconographic ambiguity, and the structure of the Iconclass hierarchy?
3. **Multimodal Enhancement:** Can curated editorial metadata improve the quality and specificity of LLM-generated image descriptions and thus boost classification accuracy?
4. **Workflow Integration:** How can AI-generated iconographic metadata be meaningfully integrated into a TEI-based editorial workflow without compromising scholarly rigor?
5. **Human Oversight:** What role does the expert-in-the-loop play, and how does human validation shape or correct machine-generated outputs?
6. Together, these questions address a central challenge: building machine-assisted systems that are not only functional but also intellectually credible and grounded in expert knowledge.

Methodology

Our approach centers on a RAG (Lewis et. al., 2020) pipeline for semi-automated Iconclass classification of complex historical imagery. Originally developed for early modern religious woodcuts, the pipeline is here adapted and refined for the manuscript miniatures of the WB.

Core Pipeline Steps

1. **Multimodal Description Generation:** An LLM (GPT-4o or 4.1) generates a natural-language description of each image. In the woodcut model, this was based on full-page visual and textual context. For the WB, we test different input configurations, including the miniature alone, the full page, and the combination of image with pre-existing editorial metadata (e.g., image titles).
2. **Vector Search with Iconclass Embeddings:** The generated description is used to perform a semantic search in a Weaviate-based vector database containing Iconclass entries. Two types of vector stores are tested: one with single-level Iconclass definitions and one augmented with all hierarchical parent levels.
3. **Retrieval-Augmented Generation:** The top-k search results are fed back into the LLM alongside the generated image description. The model is prompted to act as an art historian and select the most appropriate Iconclass code.
4. **Expert-in-the-Loop Validation:** The suggested Iconclass code and rationale are reviewed by a human expert, who accepts, rejects, or amends the result. This ensures scholarly rigor and guards against hallucination or misclassification.

Evaluation

Evaluating an AI pipeline for iconographic classification requires methods that account for the inherent ambiguity and hierarchical structure of systems like Iconclass. Because Iconclass codes are hierarchical, correctness is not binary: a classification may be partially correct even if it misses specific details. For instance, predicting "the story of David and Goliath (71H14)" still offers meaningful metadata, even if the more precise label would be "David slings a stone at Goliath's forehead (71H1442)" (Iconclass, 2025).

We calculate traditional evaluation metrics (precision, recall, and F1-score) adapted to this hierarchical structure. Precision measures how many of the predicted classification levels are correct; recall measures how many levels of the ground truth were correctly predicted; and F1-score harmonizes these values into a single performance metric.

To further account for gradations of accuracy, we apply a weighted scoring system. Predictions are assigned to one of five match categories: full match, extra match, and three types of partial matches, each with a base score reflecting its interpretive utility. These base scores are then adjusted based on the percentage of classification levels correctly matched, with penalties for incorrect levels capped to ensure informative partial matches are not overly penalized.

This multi-tiered evaluation framework offers a more nuanced picture of model performance, reflecting both the precision and scholarly usefulness of its predictions.

Data Limitations and Scope

The primary challenges encountered in this study stem from intrinsic limitations within the Iconclass taxonomy itself rather than the classification pipeline. While the Wenceslas Bible features a highly granular narrative cycle with close fidelity to the biblical text — often presenting detailed miniatures on every second page — the Iconclass vocabulary exhibits substantial coverage gaps, particularly within the Pentateuch and the Old Testament. To address this disparity, we adopt a "depth-first" annotation strategy: miniatures are labeled with the most specific code available, even when the taxonomy forces a halt at a broader category such as "Numbers (part I): from Mount Sinai to Kadesh (71E31)" (Iconclass, 2025). Furthermore, while the inherent polysemy and iconographic nuance of medieval manuscripts require expert intervention, the current phase of research prioritizes foundational tagging over exhaustive iconological exegesis. Consequently, while we acknowledge the complexity requiring domain expertise, deep interpretive analysis falls outside the scope of this evaluation framework.

Discussion

Our evaluation confirms that the RAG-based pipeline can generate accurate Iconclass classifications for medieval manuscript imagery. The model achieved an average precision of 0.5978, recall of 0.7144, and an F1 score of 0.6428. These figures demonstrate improvement over prior applications of the pipeline; particularly at the fourth and fifth levels of the Iconclass hierarchy, where our precision surpasses previous benchmarks. Moreover, this performance substantially exceeds that of our baselines: an image-retrieval method using OpenCLIP (precision 0.1694) and a traditional keyword-search approach (precision 0.462). Building on these demonstrated improvements, we position the analysis of the Wenceslas Bible as a pilot study for a generalizable workflow. We aim to explore the transferability of this methodology to divergent visual domains, such as stained glass, painting and non-biblical collections. However, establishing the boundaries of this universality remains a necessary step for future validation.

Because Iconclass is hierarchical, classification accuracy is inherently gradual rather than binary. A prediction that correctly identifies a biblical scene may still be highly useful even if it does not reach the most specific sub-action. To analyze the system's accuracy in more detail, we implemented a truncation analysis: successively removing levels from the predicted Iconclass codes and recalculating precision, recall, and F1 scores. Therefore a key feature of this approach is the model's ability to handle the varying depths of the Iconclass tree; the workflow explicitly addresses hierarchical granularities rather than treating classifications as flat labels. This analysis revealed a clear trade-off. As we truncated deeper levels, precision increased: rising

from 0.5978 at full depth (average 7.03 levels) to 0.6770 with one level truncated, 0.7410 with two levels and 0.8060 at three levels, while preserving an average depth of four levels. This improvement occurs because truncation effectively generalizes the prediction, reducing the risk of errors in specific details and increasing the likelihood of matching the broader categories in the ground truth. However, recall decreased with each truncation (from 0.7144 to 0.6978, 0.6442, and 0.5694), as the more general predictions failed to capture the full specificity of the ground truth codes.

These findings highlight that deeper specificity comes at a cost, and that optimal classification depth depends on project goals. If broad thematic tagging suffices (for search, navigation, or general annotation) a truncated Iconclass depth (e.g., four levels) may strike the best balance between precision and recall. Conversely, when fine-grained distinctions are needed, higher recall at full depth becomes more important, even if precision declines slightly. Our results also suggest that standard F1 scoring may be insufficient for evaluating Iconclass performance, as partial matches still hold scholarly value.

Our weighted scoring system addresses this by assigning interpretive value to partial matches and penalizing overly specific, incorrect predictions. This enables more nuanced evaluation, aligned with the hierarchical and contextual nature of iconographic classification.

Human validation remains essential. The expert-in-the-loop doesn't just correct output but helps define interpretive boundaries. The AI system mitigates the cold start of manual annotation, letting scholars focus on verification and refinement. This collaborative model shows that automation in the digital humanities works best when it supports, rather than replaces, expert insight.

Conclusion

This project demonstrates the feasibility and scholarly value of adapting a RAG pipeline for Iconclass classification from early modern printed material to medieval manuscript miniatures. By integrating multimodal inputs and leveraging existing editorial metadata, we achieved high precision and strong performance, especially at the fourth and fifth levels of the Iconclass hierarchy, surpassing results from our earlier woodcut study.

A key insight is the high effectiveness of a text-based approach in what is traditionally considered an image-centric task. Rather than extracting visual features with CNNs—which require large labeled datasets and extensive training—our method generates natural-language descriptions and uses them for semantic retrieval and classification. This eliminates the need for manual annotation and enables accurate classification in low-data settings, making it well-suited to historical and under-resourced collections.

Our evaluation shows that the system can deliver useful classifications even when not fully specific, thanks to Iconclass's hierarchical structure. By introducing a weighted scoring system and analyzing truncation depth, we mo-

ved beyond binary accuracy to develop a more interpretively meaningful framework for assessing AI performance in cultural heritage contexts. These tools provide curators and editors with flexible metrics to determine appropriate levels of classification detail based on institutional or scholarly goals.

Just as importantly, the project reinforces the critical role of the human expert-in-the-loop. The pipeline is designed not to replace but to accelerate expert interpretation—transforming classification from an exhaustive task into a manageable, guided review.

Ultimately, these contributions show how AI can serve as a capable and responsible collaborator in digital humanities workflows. By balancing scale with scholarly nuance, this approach lays the foundation for broader applications of iconographic metadata generation, especially for projects facing rich content and limited resources.

Fußnoten

1. Henceforth shortened as WB.

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